

Contaminated Drinking Water and Its Effect on Cancer

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ABSTRACT: Water contamination is a critical public health issue that has been linked to various adverse health outcomes including cancer. Research has shown that prolonged exposure to certain water contaminants can increase the risk of specific cancers. This study aimed to identify correlations between water contaminants and cancer incidence in Arizona. Cancer incidence data from the Arizona Cancer Registry's data dashboard and water contamination data from the environmental working group (EWG) were analyzed using Spearman's correlation. The contaminants studied included chromium, radium, uranium, nitrates, nitrites, arsenic, and disinfection byproducts (DBPs). Positive correlations were found between bladder and pancreatic cancer incidence and various contaminants studied. An association was found between colorectal cancer risk and exposure to radium and uranium in drinking water. Additionally, a statistically significant link was found between DBPs and leukemia. The findings suggest potential health risks associated with water contamination and emphasize the importance of monitoring and regulating drinking water quality to prevent adverse health outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Arizona, cancer incidence, disinfection byproducts, drinking water contaminants, environmental working group (EWG)

INTRODUCTION

This author proposed that long-term exposure to contaminated drinking water may lead to the development of certain cancers. This author's aim was to help determine what cancers are most associated with long-term exposure to contaminated drinking water. Previous researchers have shown that long-term exposure to certain contaminants through drinking water increases the risk of certain types of cancers.

In the literature on the long-term effects of contaminated water, researchers revealed that cancer was the most common long-term health hazard of contaminated water.^{1–3} Ingesting chemicals, such as nitrates and uranium, through contaminated drinking water could potentially result in the formation of N-nitroso compounds (NOC), which is a key risk factor for cancer.⁴

Chemicals, including heavy metals like arsenic, chromium, radium, and uranium, as well as disinfection byproducts (DBPs) formed during water treatment, and nitrates and nitrites, are all capable of damaging DNA. This DNA damage can lead to genetic mutations and cancer development.⁵

HEAVY METALS

Arsenic. Heavy metals like arsenic are known for their genotoxic effects, inducing DNA damage through oxidative stress, inhibition of DNA repair, and epigenetic changes.⁶ Arsenic generates reactive oxygen species (ROS) that damage DNA by causing base modifications, strand breaks, and cross-

linking.⁷ It inhibits DNA repair by targeting enzymes such as PARP and DNA ligase, leading to mutation accumulation. Additionally, arsenic causes epigenetic modifications, such as DNA methylation and histone changes, which can alter gene expression, activate oncogenes, or silence tumor suppressor genes, contributing to cancer development.⁶

Chromium. Hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) penetrates cells and is reduced to Cr(III), producing intermediates that damage DNA and generate ROS, interfering with DNA repair and leading to mutations.⁸ Cr(VI) can form DNA adducts and cause DNA strand breaks, contributing to genomic instability. Prolonged exposure to Cr(VI) can result in chronic inflammation, further promoting carcinogenesis.⁹

Radium. Radium is a naturally occurring radioactive metal that emits α particles that cause significant tissue and DNA damage when inhaled or ingested. This radiation can cause double-strand breakage in DNA, leading to mutations. Radium's α particles have high linear energy transfer (LET), meaning they deposit a substantial amount of energy over a short distance, making the damage particularly severe. This high-energy

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deposition can result in complex DNA lesions that are difficult to repair, further increasing the risk of carcinogenesis.^{10,11}

Uranium. Uranium contributes to cancer through both its chemical toxicity and its radiological properties. Its chemical toxicity primarily affects the kidneys, while its radiation can cause DNA damage like radium. The radiological properties of uranium involve the emission of α particles, which can cause double-strand breaks in DNA, leading to mutations and increased cancer risk. Additionally, uranium can generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) that induce oxidative stress and further damage DNA, contributing to genomic instability and carcinogenesis.¹²

Disinfection Byproducts (DBPs). DBPs are formed when disinfectants used in water treatment, such as chlorine, react with natural organic matter. Common DBPs include trihalomethanes (THMs) and haloacetic acids (HAAs). Some DBPs can directly interact with DNA, causing covalent modifications, such as adduct formation. These DNA adducts can result in mispairing during DNA replication, leading to mutations.¹³

Like arsenic, DBPs can also generate ROS, which can induce oxidative damage to DNA. This includes base modifications such as 8-oxoguanine, which can cause G-to-T transversions, a type of point mutation. DBPs have been shown to be cytotoxic and clastogenic, meaning they can cause chromosome breakage and rearrangements. This genomic instability is a hallmark of cancer development.¹³

Nitrates and Nitrites. The ingestion of nitrates and nitrites, particularly through contaminated drinking water or certain foods, can lead to the formation of carcinogenic nitrosamines. These nitrosamines can cause DNA damage, induce mutations, and alter gene expression through various mechanisms, ultimately contributing to the development of cancer. Understanding these pathways is crucial for assessing the risks associated with nitrate and nitrite exposure and implementing appropriate public health measures to minimize these risks.^{14,15}

Prior Studies on Water Contamination. Researchers using randomized studies evaluated community-supplied drinking water nitrate levels and cancers and established a direct link between drinking contaminated water and increased cancer risk.¹⁶ Further researchers also indicated that other water contaminants such as arsenic have the highest risk of causing different types of cancers when ingested through water.

Temkin et al.⁴ revealed that long-term exposure to nitrate contaminants in drinking water was associated with 54–82% of colorectal cancer cases reported in the United States. Picetti et al.¹⁷ also found an association between nitrates and nitrites and the development of colorectal cancer. Despite these findings, Richards et al.¹⁸ established no statistically significant relationship between nitrate contaminants in water and cancer risk. Chu et al.¹⁹ also did not find any statistically significant relationship between contaminated water and colorectal cancer. The researchers suggested the necessity for further research to determine whether a correlation or an increased risk is present between water contamination and the incidence of colorectal cancer.

In addition to nitrates and nitrites, some researchers have established that long-term exposure to chromium in drinking water increases the risks and development of certain cancers.^{3,20} Additionally, exposure to chromium-activated p53 has been found to inhibit the multiplication of cells that could potentially lead to cancer.²¹ Bjorklund et al.²² reiterated that exposure to chromium and arsenic increased the levels of reactivity and radioactivity and hence the development of cancer. Exposure to

hexavalent chromium caused respiratory cancer.³ Furthermore, exposure to arsenic compounds even at low-to-moderate levels was associated with skin cancers.²³

In additional studies, researchers revealed that drinking or using contaminated water to prepare food increased the risks of other types of cancer, including thyroid, kidney, and breast cancer in the United States.^{4,24} Exposure to high levels of arsenic, chromium, and nitrate was associated with colorectal, bladder, and kidney cancers.^{3,4}

Rationale. While in many prior studies researchers have established a possible link between contaminated drinking water and an increased risk of cancer, the specific types of cancer most associated with contaminated drinking water have not been conclusively identified. This is significant because identifying them could help public health efforts in the prevention and treatment of those cancers linked to contaminants in drinking water, thereby reducing disease burden and cost.

In the literature, researchers have made it clear that further research is needed to establish what role water contamination plays in cancer incidence. Water contaminants, such as nitrates, nitrites, arsenic, chromium, and uranium, have been linked to potential increased cancer risk. Therefore, conducting further research to identify which types of cancer are most associated with these water contaminants is important. While some researchers noted only a small association between these water contaminants and cancers, others concluded that the association was quite strong, indicating that further research was needed to identify the strength of the relationship between contaminants and cancers of the colon, stomach, kidney, liver, and bladder.

Significance. Given the existing body of literature on the topic, a relationship between contaminated drinking water and cancer seems likely. Previous researchers have recommended that the relationship between the two be further investigated. While prior research into water quality and contamination often focused on the short-term effects of contamination and infectious diseases, more recent researchers have begun to focus on the long-term effects, including the development of certain types of cancers. Additional research is needed to address this gap in the literature by investigating the extent to which contaminated water is related to different categories of cancers using historical data.

■ EXPERIMENTAL/METHODS

Study Design. This study is a correlational analysis in which this author aimed to investigate the relationship between contaminated drinking water and cancer incidence in Arizona. This author used public data sources, which included cancer incidence rates and water contamination data by county. The dependent variable was cancer incidence, and the independent variable was water quality. This author determined whether a statistically significant relationship existed between the two variables through the use of correlation coefficient analysis.

Data Collection. Contaminated drinking water data were obtained from the Environmental Working Group (EWG) website.²⁵ The data included the level of contaminants in drinking water across Arizona from 2014–2019. The cancer incidence data were obtained from the Arizona Cancer Registry's data dashboard.²⁶ This data included the number of reportable cancers in Arizona during the same period and was categorized by cancer site and county.

Data Analysis. To analyze the relationship between contaminated drinking water and cancer incidence, this author used Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, which is a

Figure 1. Total Number of Facilities by County Reporting Water Contaminants.

nonparametric statistical test used to measure the association between two variables.²⁷ The significance level was set at $p < 0.5$. Spearman's correlation was conducted using IBM SPSS statistical software (Version 29), which was appropriate for this study because the data was continuous and its distribution non-normal.

The following cancer sites were analyzed: bladder, colorectal, female breast, female gynecologic, kidney and renal pelvis, leukemia, liver, lung, melanoma, pancreas, prostate, and stomach. Two additional categories, all types of cancers and total cancer cases (see [Definitions](#) Section), were also analyzed in this study. Additionally, this author analyzed nine different water contaminants, including arsenic, chromium, nitrates, nitrites, radium, uranium, and the DBPs (HAA5, HAA9, and TTHMs).

The publicly available water contamination data abstracted from the EWG website were weighted using facility population sizes to control for differences in facility size that may have an impact on drinking water contamination levels. To determine whether water quality and cancer incidence were significantly associated, a weighted correlation analysis was conducted.

Definitions. All types of cancer refers to any reportable cancer types identified within a specific county over a 6 year period from 2014–2019. This definition is inclusive of other primary cancer sites that were separately studied.

Total cancers are the total raw number of reportable cases per county during the time frame 2014–2019. This number was not based on the population of the county.

Female gynecologic sites included corpus uteri, uterus, cervix uteri, and ovary and were combined into a single category due to the low numbers of individual sites in some counties.

Ethical Considerations and Informed Consent. This author only used publicly available data, and no human subjects were involved. Therefore, no ethical concerns were relevant to this study. No participant recruitment or informed consent was required for this study because the data used were from publicly available sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 747 facilities that provided drinking water in Arizona were included in the study. Data on the presence of

contaminants in drinking water were obtained from the EWG website from 2014 to 2019. Several different types of contaminants were reported by the facilities. This author focused on nine different contaminants that were noted during the literature review to be known or suspected carcinogens.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of water contamination by county. Of the 747 facilities that reported contamination, 147 facilities (19.7%) were in Pima County, 105 facilities (14.1%) were in Maricopa County, and 104 facilities (13.9%) were in Yavapai County. Despite Maricopa County having the largest population of the counties by far, Pima County had more facilities reporting water contamination data. This is partially explained by the City of Phoenix water utility, which serves many residents of Maricopa County. According to the EWG,²⁵ this water utility serves 1,579,000 people in Maricopa County, which was by far the largest number of people served by any single water facility in the state.

The City of Tucson water utility provides drinking water to 675,686 residents in Pima County, which equates to nearly 70% of the population in that county.²⁵ Most counties have a few facilities that provide for a large percentage of the county's residents, and the City of Tucson water system is especially notable in this regard.

Shapiro-Wilk Normality Testing. Results from the Shapiro-Wilk normality testing revealed significant results for all the water contamination variables except for arsenic. Chromium, nitrates, TTHM, HAA5, HAA9, radium combined, nitrates and nitrites, and uranium all had values less than .05, including the weighted values. However, the value for arsenic (nonweighted) was .452, indicating that it was not statistically significant. The mean for arsenic was 3.9162, and the Standard Deviation (SD) was 2.12761. All the cancer data variables were found to be statistically significant on the Shapiro-Wilk normality testing. The results of this test indicated that the sample is not likely normally distributed. [Table 1](#) shows the median and interquartile ranges for all the contaminants (weighted values). [Table 2](#) shows the median and interquartile range for all of the cancer types.

Spearman's Correlation Coefficient Analysis. Spearman's correlation coefficient analysis was performed on nine water contaminants across various cancer sites, including

Table 1. Median and Interquartile Range for Water Contamination Data^a

contaminant	median	IQR
chromium (ppb)	4.0026	3.27
HAA5 (ppb)	4.6780	9.97
HAA9 (ppb)	8.1975	17.73
nitrate (ppm)	2.5090	1.29
nitrate and nitrite (ppm)	2.4440	1.48
radium (pCi/L)	0.1377	0.16
TTHM (ppb)	24.7690	29.85
uranium (pCi/L)	1.8790	1.09

^aThe mean for arsenic was 3.9162, and the SD was 2.12761. It was not included in this table because its distribution was normal.

Table 2. Median and Interquartile Range for Cancer Incidence^a

type	median	IQR
all cancers	396.00	21.6
total cancers	11,382.50	104,066
bladder	18.60	3.9
colorectal	32.30	1.2
breast	115.90	14.8
female GYN	40.10	1.8
kidney and renal pelvis	16.650	2.0
leukemia and lymphoma	27.40	3.4
liver	7.50	1.6
lung	44.40	3.0
melanoma	28.90	9.4
pancreas	11.90	1.2
prostate	80.80	10.9
stomach	5.250	0.8

^aData on female GYN cancers, leukemia and lymphomas, liver, pancreas, and stomach were not available for Greenlee County. Stomach cancer data were not available for Graham County as well. All Cancers are the incidence rates per 100,00 residents of a given county, which includes all reportable cancer types diagnosed from 2014 to 2019. Total Cancers are the actual number of diagnosed cancer cases within the same time period, without taking into account the population size of the county.

bladder, colorectal, female breast, female gynecological sites (which encompassed corpus uteri, uterus, cervix uteri, and ovary), kidney and renal pelvis, leukemia and lymphoma, liver, lung, melanoma of the skin, pancreas, prostate, and stomach.

The majority of the selected cancer sites were based on extensive literature reviews, indicating that they were most likely associated with water contamination. However, some of the more prevalent cancer sites, like lung and melanoma of the skin, had not been identified during the initial literature review but were included due to their incidence rates.²⁶

Figure 2 presents the positive results of Spearman's correlation coefficient analysis, which was used to investigate the association between water contaminants and cancer sites. The coefficient values indicate the strength and direction of the correlation, with a value closer to 1 indicating a stronger positive correlation. Among all of the water contaminants, the highest positive correlation was observed for chromium and bladder cancer ($r = 0.791$).

Nitrate and HAA9 were found to be associated with the highest number of cancer sites, with six different sites showing significant positive associations. Among the nine different cancer sites studied, pancreatic cancer showed the most significant

association with water contamination. Six different water contaminants were found to be positively associated with the pancreas.

Interestingly, many of the water contaminants had a negative correlation with certain cancer types and outcomes. Figure 3 presents the negative results of the Spearman's correlation coefficient analysis. Among all the water contaminants, the highest negative correlation was observed for chromium and kidney and renal pelvis cancers ($r = -0.727$).

Although there were many negative correlations between water contaminants and cancer incidence, noting that this does not imply that a lack of relationship between the two variables is important. A negative correlation simply suggests that as one variable increases, the other decreases. In this case, it is possible that the water contaminants are indeed related to cancer incidence, but other factors may mask the relationship. Further research is necessary to fully understand the impacts of water contaminants on cancer incidence.

Table 3 displays the variables that had no significant correlation, either positive or negative. Among the water contaminants tested, HAA5 had the highest number of variables with no significant correlations with cancer outcomes, with six such variables, followed by TTHMs with five and radium with four.

Due to missing cancer data for certain cancer sites in Greenlee County, this county was excluded from correlations involving those cancer sites. Specifically, data were not available for female gynecological cancers, leukemias, lymphomas, liver, pancreatic, or stomach cancer in Greenlee County. Stomach cancer data were also not available for Graham County. Additionally, Greenlee County, Graham County, and La Paz County were excluded from variable analyses of HAA9 due to missing water contamination information. Therefore, any correlations or relationships involving HAA9 should be interpreted with caution and do not necessarily reflect the conditions in these three counties. It is unlikely, however, that the exclusion of these three counties significantly affected the overall results due to their small populations and rural nature.

In summary, this author examined the relationship between water contaminants and cancer outcomes by analyzing data from all of the counties in Arizona. The results of the analysis show that some water contaminants, such as nitrate and HAA9, are significantly associated with cancer outcomes, while others are not. The highest positive correlation was observed for chromium and bladder cancer ($r = 0.791$). Six different water contaminants were found to be positively associated with pancreatic cancer, with a varying range of correlation coefficients from low to moderate, and all were statistically significant. Overall, the findings suggested that reducing exposure to certain water contaminants may help reduce cancer risk in communities. However, further research is needed to confirm these findings and determine the best strategies for reducing exposure to water contaminants.

Significant Associations. The results of this author's quantitative correlational research study revealed a robust correlation between the water contaminants investigated and multiple types of cancer outcomes. Among the notable findings, this author's study showed that pancreatic cancer displayed the greatest number of positive correlations with six distinct water contaminants (nitrate, nitrite, TTHM, HAA5, HAA9, and chromium), followed by bladder with five (chromium, arsenic, nitrite, nitrate, and uranium). Leukemia was also found to be associated with DBPs.

Figure 2. Positive Correlations Coefficient by Cancer Type & Water Contaminant Note. Greenlee, Graham, and La Paz counties were excluded from the variable analyses of HAA9 due to missing water contamination information. Data on female GYN cancers, leukemia and lymphomas, liver, pancreas, and stomach were not available for Greenlee County. Stomach cancer data were not available for Graham County as well.

Figure 3. Negative Correlations Coefficient by Cancer Type and Water Contaminant Note. Greenlee, Graham, and La Paz counties were excluded from the variable analyses of HAA9 due to missing water contamination information. Data on female GYN cancers, leukemia and lymphomas, liver, pancreas, and stomach were not available for Greenlee County. Stomach cancer data was not available for Graham County as well.

Congruencies with Existing Literature. Bladder Cancer and Chromium Exposure. Our study found a strong positive correlation between chromium exposure and bladder cancer incidence, consistent with previous research. El-Kady and Abdel-Wahhab²⁰ reported that long-term exposure to chromium in drinking water is associated with an increased risk of bladder cancer. Similarly, Bjorklund et al.²² emphasized the carcinogenic potential of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)), particularly its association with respiratory and bladder cancers.

Pancreatic Cancer and Multiple Contaminants. The significant associations between pancreatic cancer and multiple water contaminants (nitrates, nitrites, TTHMs, HAA5, HAA9, and chromium) align with the findings from other studies. For instance, Temkin et al.⁴ reported that nitrates in drinking water are linked to an increased risk of colorectal and pancreatic cancers. This is further supported by Picetti et al.,¹⁷ who found a

similar association between nitrates, nitrites, and gastrointestinal cancers.

Leukemia and Disinfection Byproducts (DBPs). This author found strong positive associations between exposure to HAA5, HAA9, and TTHMs in drinking water and an increased risk of leukemia. This is in line with results from other studies. For example, Kasim et al.²⁸ found that exposure to DBPs, such as HAA5, was significantly associated with an increased risk of leukemia. Additionally, Foster et al.²⁹ found that higher levels of TTHMs were associated with an elevated incidence of leukemia in adult populations. Taken together, the authors of these studies provide further evidence that exposure to DBPs, including HAA5, HAA9, and TTHM, may be a potential risk factor for leukemia.

Inconsistencies and Areas for Further Investigation. Water Contamination and Colorectal Cancer Risk. While our

Table 3. No Significant Correlation Found^a

water contaminant—cancer site	Spearman's correlation coefficient
arsenic-pancreas	0.015
chromium-prostate	0.042
HAA5-bladder	0.027
HAA5-breast	0.029
HAA5-kidneyRP	0.022
HAA5-liver	0.057
HAA5-prostate	0.057
HAA5-stomach	0.044
HAA9-bladder	0.070
HAA9-prostate	0.051
nitrate-female GYN	0.036
nitrate-prostate	0.043
nitrite-leuk/Lymph	0.023
nitrite-prostate	0.035
radium-bladder	0.058
radium-lung	0.032
radium-pancreas	0.006
radium-stomach	0.014
TTHMs-bladder	0.021
TTHMs-kidneyRP	0.031
TTHMs-lung	0.005
TTHMs-prostate	0.034
TTHMs-stomach	0.045
Uranium-all	0.065
uranium-prostate	0.060

^aGreenlee, Graham, and La Paz counties were excluded from the variable analyses of HAA9 due to missing water contamination information. Data on female GYN cancers, leukemia and lymphomas, liver, pancreas, and stomach were not available for Greenlee County. Stomach cancer data was not available for Graham County as well.

study found associations between radium and uranium in drinking water and colorectal cancer, the effect sizes were smaller compared to other findings. Previous research presents mixed results: Temkin et al.⁴ and Picetti et al.¹⁷ reported strong associations between nitrate contamination and colorectal cancer, whereas Chu et al.¹⁹ and Richards et al.¹⁸ found no significant relationship. These inconsistencies suggest that the relationship between water contaminants and colorectal cancer may be complex and influenced by additional factors not accounted for in all studies.

Limited Evidence for Water Contaminants and Stomach Cancer. Our study found limited evidence linking water contaminants to stomach cancer, with only a weak positive association observed with HAA9. Previous studies, such as Acosta et al.,³⁰ suggested a potential link between water contamination and stomach cancer, particularly due to *Helicobacter pylori* infection. However, our findings did not strongly support this, indicating the need for further research to clarify these relationships.

Confounding Factors and Alternative Hypotheses. We acknowledge that several potential confounding factors could influence the observed associations. Socioeconomic status, lifestyle factors such as smoking and diet, and other environmental exposures might confound the relationships between water contaminants and cancer incidence. Future studies should control these variables to better isolate the effects of water contaminants. Additionally, alternative hypotheses, such as the presence of multiple interacting contaminants or indirect effects

mediated through other health conditions, should be explored to fully understand the observed correlations.

Biological Mechanisms. In examining the biological mechanisms by which water contaminants might trigger cancer onset, we identified several pathways through which heavy metals (arsenic, chromium, radium, and uranium), disinfection byproducts, nitrates, and nitrites can cause carcinogenic effects. These include:

- **Oxidative Stress:** Many of these contaminants generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to oxidative damage to DNA, proteins, and lipids. This oxidative stress can initiate a cascade of cellular damage that contributes to cancer development.³¹
- **DNA Damage:** Contaminants like arsenic and chromium can cause direct DNA damage, resulting in mutations that can initiate cancer. Chromium(VI) and arsenic have been shown to form DNA adducts and induce DNA strand breaks, leading to genomic instability.^{7,8}
- **Inhibition of DNA Repair Processes:** Some contaminants inhibit the activity of key DNA repair enzymes, preventing the repair of DNA damage and leading to mutation accumulation. For example, arsenic inhibits the activity of enzymes such as PARP and DNA ligase, which are crucial for DNA repair.⁶
- **Epigenetic Changes:** Contaminants can cause changes in DNA methylation and histone modification, altering gene expression patterns in ways that can promote cancer. Epigenetic modifications induced by contaminants can lead to the activation of oncogenes or the silencing of tumor suppressor genes, thereby contributing to carcinogenesis.¹³

Theoretical and Practical Applications. The findings of this study have several theoretical and practical applications. Theoretical applications involve providing valuable insights into the relationship between water contamination and cancer outcomes and contributing to our understanding of the potential health effects associated with exposure to contaminants in drinking water. Moreover, the study can serve as a foundation for the long-term effects of exposure to environmental toxins.

From a practical standpoint, this study can provide valuable information to policymakers, public health officials, and water suppliers regarding strategies to prevent and mitigate water contamination and its associated health risks. As the results indicate, improving the quality of drinking water could potentially lead to a reduction in certain cancer incidents. Therefore, water suppliers and policymakers can work toward implementing measures that will reduce exposure to contaminants and improve public health.

Public Health Implications. The results of this study emphasize the importance of translating these findings into practical water quality management strategies with significant public health benefits. Practical strategies might include:

- **Enhanced Water Monitoring and Regulation:** Implement stricter monitoring and regulation of water quality to ensure contaminants are kept below harmful levels.
- **Improved Water Treatment Technologies:** Invest in advanced water treatment technologies that can effectively remove contaminants from drinking water.
- **Public Awareness and Education:** Raise public awareness about the potential health risks associated with water contaminants and educate communities on measures to reduce exposure.

- Policy and Legislation: Advocate for stronger policies and legislation that protect water sources from contamination and ensure safe drinking water standards are maintained.

Limitations. While this author provided valuable insights into the relationship between water contamination and cancer outcomes in Arizona, a few limitations in the study should be considered. First, while this author utilized data from a large sample size, covering most of the counties in Arizona, for two small rural counties, Greenlee and Graham, cancer outcome data were missing. Additionally, Greenlee, Graham, and La Paz counties did not report HAA9 water contamination information to the EWG website. However, due to the small size of these counties, their exclusion is not likely to have significant impacts on the overall results of the study.

Correlational Analysis Design. Additionally, while this author employed Spearman correlation analysis to examine the relationship between water contamination and cancer outcomes, noting that this type of analysis cannot establish causality is important. A more comprehensive investigation into the underlying causations and mechanisms that link water contaminants to cancer is needed. Future studies should aim to explore the specific mechanisms by which water contaminants can cause cancer and other potential confounding factors that could be linked to cancer. This study involved a population-based sample, and there may be differences in the exposure to water contaminants and cancer prevalence between different subpopulations. Future studies could investigate these differences in more detail.

Generalizability. Furthermore, while the study provides valuable insights into the association between water contaminants and cancer prevalence in Arizona, the results may not be directly generalizable or transferable to other populations due to the relatively homogeneous population in Arizona. Future studies could investigate the association between water contaminants and cancer in other regions with similar population demographics, such as other mountain and southwestern states, such as Colorado or New Mexico, to determine whether the results are replicable in other populations with similar characteristics.

Data Limitations. In addition to the points mentioned above, there are several limitations inherent in the cancer registry data used in this study. First, despite mandatory reporting, under-reporting or incomplete reporting of cancer cases can still occur, particularly in regions with less comprehensive healthcare infrastructure or due to inconsistencies in data collection practices. Second, variations in healthcare access can result in disparities in cancer diagnosis rates; populations with limited access to healthcare may be underdiagnosed or undiagnosed, skewing the data. Third, differences in diagnostic and reporting standards across regions or facilities may affect the accuracy and consistency of the data, making it difficult to compare findings. Lastly, there may be time lags in data collection, resulting in incomplete or outdated data, particularly for recent cancer cases.^{32,33}

Recommendations for Future Research. Based on this author's findings, several areas are recommended for future research. First, the relationship between chromium exposure and bladder cancer should be explored in more depth, including investigating the specific mechanisms through which this toxic metal may increase the risk of developing this cancer type. Additionally, given that pancreatic and bladder cancers were associated with the most water contaminants in this study, future

research should investigate the potential health effects of other commonly occurring environmental toxins. Considering the synergistic effects of multiple contaminants on cancer development, as well as how environmental justice issues may lead to disparities in water quality and associated health outcomes, would also be valuable.

Future studies should also aim to investigate the underlying mechanisms by which water contaminants can cause cancer with a particular focus on the molecular pathways involved. Additional research is needed to identify other potential confounding factors that could be linked to cancer and develop strategies to control these factors in future studies.

Additionally, there should be more research into the impact of exposure to water contaminants in specific subpopulations, such as children or elderly populations, who may be more sensitive to the effects of these contaminants. Finally, future studies could investigate potential interventions and strategies to reduce exposure to water contaminants and mitigate the risk of cancer in populations with high levels of exposure. Overall, further research could help to better understand the complex relationships between environmental toxins, water quality, and human health and inform policies to protect public health.

CONCLUSIONS

Spearman correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between water contaminants and cancer outcomes in Arizona using water contamination data from the EWG website and cancer incidence rates from the Arizona Cancer Data Dashboard. This author found that several water contaminants were positively correlated with an increased incidence of both bladder and pancreatic cancers. A particularly strong correlation existed between exposure to chromium and the incidence of bladder cancer. Additionally, exposure to DBPs in drinking water was found to be strongly associated with an increased risk of leukemia. This author also identified a significant association between exposure to radium and uranium in drinking water and an increased risk of colorectal cancer. Overall, these findings illustrate the crucial significance of upholding the quality and safety of our water sources. They emphasized the need for increased vigilance in identifying and mitigating potential water hazards not only in Arizona but also across the world. The necessity of this action was further underscored by the confirmed associations between water contaminants and the cancer outcomes identified in this study.

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

REFERENCES

- (1) Donovan, E.; Unice, K.; Roberts, J. D.; Harris, M.; Finley, B. Risk of gastrointestinal disease associated with exposure to pathogens in the

- water of the Lower Passaic River. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **2008**, *74* (4), 994–1003.
- (2) Hosseini, F.; Majdi, M.; Naghshi, S.; Sheikhhosseini, F.; Djafarian, K.; Shab-Bidar, S. Nitrate-nitrite exposure through drinking water and diet and risk of colorectal cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Clin. Nutr.* **2021**, *40* (5), 3073–3081.
- (3) Lin, L.; Yang, H.; Xu, X. Effects of water pollution on human health and disease heterogeneity: A Review. *Front. Environ. Sci.* **2022**, *10*, No. 880246, DOI: 10.3389/fenvs.2022.880246.
- (4) Temkin, A.; Evans, S.; Manidis, T.; Campbell, C.; Naidenko, O. V. Exposure-based assessment and economic valuation of adverse birth outcomes and cancer risk due to nitrate in United States drinking water. *Environ. Res.* **2019**, *176*, No. 108442.
- (5) Smith, I. Water pollution and cancer: An updated review. *Sci. Insights* **2023**, *43* (4), 1079–1086.
- (6) Stößer, S.; Lump, T.; Fischer, F.; Gunesch, S.; Schumacher, P.; Hartwig, A. Effect of long-term low-dose arsenic exposure on DNA methylation and gene expression in human liver cells. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2023**, *24* (20), No. 15238.
- (7) Henkler, F.; Brinkmann, J.; Luch, A. The role of oxidative stress in carcinogenesis induced by metals and xenobiotics. *Cancers* **2010**, *2* (2), 376–396.
- (8) Singh, V.; Singh, N.; Verma, M.; Kamal, R.; Tiwari, R.; Chivate, M. S.; Rai, S. N.; Kumar, A.; Singh, A.; Singh, M. P.; Vamanu, E.; Mishra, V. Hexavalent-chromium induced oxidative stress and the protective role of antioxidants against cellular toxicity. *Antioxidants* **2022**, *11* (12), No. 2375.
- (9) Zhitkovich, A. Chromium in drinking water: sources, metabolism, and cancer risks. *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* **2011**, *24* (10), 1617–1629.
- (10) Dornish, M.; Heier-Baardson, H.; Pettersen, E. Cellular effects of alpha particle radiation from radium-223: Alpharadin, a new radiopharmaceutical for the treatment of skeletal metastases. *Cancer Res.* **2008**, *68* (9), No. 5749.
- (11) Parker, C.; Nilsson, S.; Heinrich, D.; Helle, S. I.; O’Sullivan, J. M.; Fossa, S. D.; Sartor, O.; et al. Alpha emitter radium-223 and survival in metastatic prostate cancer. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2013**, *369* (3), 213–223.
- (12) Craft, E. S.; Abu-Qare, A. W.; Flaherty, M. M.; Garfolo, M. C.; Rincavage, H. L.; Abou-Donia, M. B. Depleted and natural uranium: chemistry and toxicological effects. *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health, Part B* **2004**, *7* (4), 297–317.
- (13) Richardson, S. D.; Plewa, M. J.; Wagner, E. D.; Schoeny, R.; DeMarini, D. M. Occurrence, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity of regulate and emerging disinfection by-products in drinking water: a review and roadmap for research. *Mutat. Res., Rev. Mutat. Res.* **2007**, *636* (1–3), 178–242.
- (14) Bryan, N. S.; Loscalzo, J. *Nitrite and Nitrate in Human Health and Disease*; Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- (15) Ward, M. H.; Jones, R. R.; Brender, J. D.; de Kok, T. M.; Weyer, P. J.; Nolan, B. T.; Villanueva, C.; Van Breda, S. G. Drinking water nitrate and human health: an updated review. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2018**, *15* (7), No. 1557.
- (16) Zhang, J.; Liu, L.; Chen, F. Production and characterization of exopolysaccharides from *Chlorella zofingiensis* and *Chlorella Vulgaris* with anti-colorectal cancer activity. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2019**, *134*, 976–983.
- (17) Picetti, R.; Deeney, M.; Pastorino, S.; Miller, M. R.; Shah, A.; Leon, D. A.; Dangour, A. D.; Green, R. Nitrate and nitrite contamination in drinking water and cancer risk: A systematic review with meta-analysis. *Environ. Res.* **2022**, *210*, No. 112988.
- (18) Richards, J.; Chambers, T.; Hales, S.; Joy, M.; Radu, T.; Woodward, A.; Baker, M. G.; et al. Nitrate contamination in drinking water and colorectal cancer: Exposure assessment and estimated health burden in New Zealand. *Environ. Res.* **2022**, *204*, No. 112322.
- (19) Chu, T. H.; Chou, Y. W.; Lin, S. L.; Lin, S. F.; Chen, H. H.; Hu, W. H.; Huang, C. C. A pilot study examining the relationship between environmental contaminants and colorectal cancer at a single medical institute in Taiwan. *Taiwan Gong Gong Wei Sheng Za Zhi* **2021**, *40* (4), 382–393.
- (20) El-Kady, A. A.; Abdel-Wahhab, M. A. Occurrence of trace metals in foodstuffs and their health impact. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* **2018**, *75*, 36–45.
- (21) New-Aaron, M.; Naveed, Z.; Rogan, E. G. Estrogen Disrupting Pesticides in Nebraska Groundwater: Trends between Pesticide-contaminated Water and Estrogen-related Cancers in An Ecological Observational Study. *Water* **2021**, *13* (6), No. 790.
- (22) Björklund, G.; Semenova, Y.; Pivina, L.; Dadar, M.; Rahman, M. M.; Aaseth, J.; Chirumbolo, S. Uranium in drinking water: A public health threat. *Arch. Toxicol.* **2020**, *94* (5), 1551–1560.
- (23) Chen, Y.; Parvez, F.; Gamble, M.; Islam, T.; Ahmed, A.; Argos, M.; Baron, J. A. Arsenic exposure at low-to-moderate levels and skin lesions, arsenic metabolism, neurological functions, and biomarkers for respiratory and cardiovascular diseases: Review of recent findings from the Health Effects of Arsenic Longitudinal Study (HEALS) in Bangladesh. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* **2009**, *239* (2), 184–192.
- (24) Brody, J. G.; Aschengrau, A.; McKelvey, W.; Swartz, C. H.; Kennedy, T.; Rudel, R. A. Breast cancer risk and drinking water contaminated by wastewater: A case control study. *Environ. Health* **2006**, *5* (1), No. 28.
- (25) Environmental Working Group. National Tap Water Database. <https://www.ewg.org/tapwater/> accessed May 30, 2023.
- (26) Arizona Department of Health Services. Arizona Cancer Registry. <https://www.azdhs.gov/preparedness/public-health-statistics/cancer-registry/index.php#data-dashboard> accessed May 30, 2023.
- (27) Spearman, C. The proof and measurement of association between two things. *Am. J. Psychol.* **1904**, *15* (1), 72–101.
- (28) Kasim, K.; Levallois, P.; Johnson, K. C.; Abdous, B.; Auger, P. Chlorination disinfection by-products in drinking water and the risk of adult leukemia in Canada. *Am. J. Epidemiol.* **2006**, *163* (2), 116–126.
- (29) Foster, A. J.; Prentice, A.; Copplestone, J. A.; Cartwright, R.; Ricketts, C. The distribution of leukemia in association with domestic water quality in South West England. *Eur. J. Cancer Prev.* **1997**, *6* (1), 11–19.
- (30) Acosta, C. P.; Benavides, J. A.; Sierra, C. H. Qualitative analysis of water quality deterioration and infection by *Helicobacter pylori* in a community with high risk of stomach cancer (Cauca, Colombia). *Salud Colectiva* **2015**, *11* (4), No. 575.
- (31) Moloney, J. N.; Cotter, T. G. ROS Signaling in the biology of cancer. *Semin. Cell Dev. Biol.* **2018**, *80*, 50–64.
- (32) North American Association of Central Cancer Registries (NAACCR). Assessment of Central Cancer Registry Timeliness and Reporting, 2021. <https://www.naacr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Full-Report-Year-1.pdf>.
- (33) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). National Program of Cancer Registries (NPCR) Program Standards, 2022. https://stacks.cdc.gov/view/cdc/113808/cdc_113808_DS1.pdf.